

**EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT
OF THE STATE OF CURE OF THE MATRIX
ON THE PROPERTIES OF GLASS-FIBRE
EPOXY RESIN LAMINATES**

by K. PHILLIPS and M. G. BADER

*Department of Metallurgy and Materials Technology,
University of Surrey*

ABSTRACT

The state of cure of the matrix in thermoplastic modified and orthodox epoxy/glass composites was studied using D.S.C. and T.M.A. techniques. It was not possible to correlate the 'degree of cure' from these thermal analysis techniques with the room temperature mechanical properties of unidirectional laminates, obtained from interlaminar shear and double torsion tests. The strain energy release rate at elevated temperatures is sensitive to the cure schedule used in fabricating the laminate.

INTRODUCTION

The short term mechanical properties of fibre reinforced plastics laminates are most strongly dependent upon the properties of the fibre and the laminate geometry, and to a much lesser degree by the choice of matrix resin and fabrication route. We are concerned with the effect of variability in the matrix structure and properties, as influenced by the processing route, on the long term performance of the laminate, especially with regard to fatigue [1] and resistance to environmental hazards. Amongst the reasons for undertaking the present study are: The suggestion that the fatigue characteristics of glass-fibre/epoxy composites are improved if the resin is somewhat undercured. Also there is often a difficulty, when fabricating large scale components or structures, in accurately following the standard cure schedules for the resin, as heat-up and cool-down periods are necessarily extended on account of the sheer mass of material involved.

The initial aim of the present study has been to investigate a number of possible physical and mechanical techniques which might indicate the "state of cure" of an epoxy resin matrix, and to correlate the results with both the cure schedules used and the mechanical properties of the laminates produced.

The epoxy resins used in composite laminates are complex proprietary formulations. Their constitution is optimised for the particular fabrication route and to give an acceptable combination of long shelf life with a convenient curing schedule. During curing the liquid resin is transformed into a cross-linked network structure. There are often several competing chemical reactions and the final cured state is dependent on the precise thermal history of the resin.

In this preliminary work we have chosen one prepreg system and one wet lamination system for investigation of different curing schedules and have evaluated their "state of cure" by thermal analysis, a double torsion fracture energy test and interlaminar shear tests.

MATERIALS AND FABRICATION

The prepreg (PR series) was a proprietary system using unidirectional glass-fibre impregnated with a thermoplastic modified polyfunctional epoxy resin using a latent solid state curing agent (Ciba-Geigy BSL 913). The recommended cure schedule was to heat at 120°C for one hour. At this temperature the fine particles of the curing agent (dicyandiamide - DICY) first dissolve in the resin whereupon the curing reaction(s) proceed rapidly. We have varied the curing schedule to include a pre-cure period at 90°C followed by various combinations of temperature and time for the final cure. The laminates were assembled from sixteen 200x200mm layers of the prepreg, stacked to form a unidirectional laminate. The pack was cured in a vacuum bag in a platen press. Some additional small laminates were also fabricated by straight hot press moulding.

The wet lay up system (WL series) was an amine cured epoxy (Ciba-Geigy LY 556/HT 972). Glass rovings were wound onto an open frame to form a uniaxial array of fibres which were then wetted out with the liquid resin in a vacuum oven, and hot press-moulded. An excess of resin was applied and this was squeezed out along the fibre direction during pressing. This technique allowed the fabrication of high quality laminates with good fibre collimation and very low porosity. These laminates were cured at temperatures spanning the range 110-190°C, the "recommended" temperature being 160°C.

Test pieces were cut from the plaques and then stored in a controlled environment, 20°C and 50% RH, for 28 days before testing.

THERMAL ANALYSIS

The initial work was to test samples of both prepreg and resin of the type used in the prepreg in a differential scanning calorimeter, DSC, (Dupont 990). A preliminary study on another resin system (Fothergill & Harvey Code 69) had indicated that this technique might be sensitive to the degree of cure [2]. The technique was to heat the sample from room temperature to approximately 250°C at 5 deg C/min and to record the thermogram (i.e. temperature differential between sample and standard versus temperature) as shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1 D.S.C. traces for cured and uncured samples of Code 69 prepreg. The percentage cure is defined as $(A-B)/A$. [2].

Fig.2 D.S.C. traces for cured and uncured PR series prepreg.

The uncured material gave a characteristic thermogram which indicated three distinct exotherm regions over the temperature range. The baseline was set by scanning a sample which had been arbitrarily overcured by heating, in the cell, to 250°C. The "degree of cure" may then be expressed by comparing the area under the curve (this is proportional to the total cure exotherm) of the sample with that of the uncured sample, i.e. the areas indicated "A" and "B" in Figure 1. Three different cure schedules were applied and the results are shown in Table 1 below.

TABLE 1

Cure Schedule	Percentage Cure	
Heat to 170°C at 2°C min ⁻¹ and hold 1 hr.	83	± 0.7
½ hr. at 120°C + 8 hr. at 140°C	78	± 3.2
1 hr. at 120°C + 1 hr. at 170°C	82	± 1.8

These cure schedules appear to give similar "degrees of cure" within the sensitivity and experimental variability of this technique. On applying the DSC technique to the PR resin and prepreg no significant variation could be detected since a very pronounced single exotherm occurred and there was a negligible variation in the traces from the partially cured materials, Figure 2. We conclude that this DSC technique is insufficiently sensitive to detect the variations of cure with thermal history relevant to this system.

Isothermal experiments in which ΔT was plotted against time at constant temperature yielded thermograms of similar general form to those produced in the scanning mode. The exothermic peaks, in these runs, initiate as soon as the cell reaches the set temperature, and there is no induction period, even at the lowest temperature (85°C). The time to the peak exotherm may be taken as an indication of the reaction rate, and if we assume that an Arrhenius type of rate equation applies, then a plot of the reciprocal of the reciprocal temperature against the logarithm of reciprocal time to the exothermic peak should be linear, Figure 3.

Fig 3. Arrhenius plot of isothermal cure temperature against time to exothermic peak for PR series prepreg and resin.

Fig. 4 Comparison of penetration and 3-point bend techniques for determining softening temperatures in the T.M.A.

It is, however, not possible to obtain accurate reaction rates from these isothermal thermograms, so we have not attempted to calculate energies.

We then investigated the effects of the cure schedule by measuring the softening point of the material. A conventional softening point (e.g. Vicat) determination is carried out by heating a sample whilst a probe is applied to it under a constant force. The extent of penetration of the probe is measured and the softening point is defined in terms of the stress and temperature at which an arbitrary degree of penetration occurs. This technique is not suitable for a composite because the glass fibres offer additional resistance to the probe, and furthermore the degree of penetration is sensitive to fibre orientation.

Accordingly we have developed a test whereby a small rectangular sample approximately 11x2x2mm with the fibres aligned in the transverse direction is set up as a three-point bend specimen under a load of ~30 gf in the Dupont 942 Thermomechanical Analyser. The deflection of the beam is measured as the temperature is raised at 10 deg C/min. A comparison of the penetration and bend softening point tests is shown in Figure 4. The latter proved to be much more sensitive because the reinforcement contributes little to the bending characteristics of a beam of the configuration used.

This softening point technique was used to study the effect of varying the length of time that the laminate is held at the pre-cure temperature of 90°C and the cure temperature of 120°C, and the role of post-cure times and temperatures on the curing process of the PR system. Unidirectional PR laminates were pre-cured at 90°C for up to four hours and then cut into sections which were further cured at 120°C for between one and four hours, Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 T.M.A. results from PR laminates with a variety of pre-cure (90°C)/cure (120°C) schedules.

Fig. 6 Softening temperature as a function of post-cure times and temperatures for a PR laminate cured for one hour at 120°C.

The softening point appears to be determined solely by the final curing time and is not influenced by the pre-cure. Curing appears to be substantially complete after 2 hours, although the softening point continues to rise slightly on further heating. The post-cure test results were obtained from a laminate cured at 120°C for an hour and then cut into sections which were post-cured over a range of times and temperatures. The softening point of the PR laminate, shown in Fig. 6, is relatively insensitive to the post-cure temperature, but again rises with increasing post-cure time up to 6 hours. The drop in the softening point of the laminate held at 190°C for six hours indicates the onset of degradation of the resin.

'Degree of Cure' studies on laminates from the WL series were restricted to single stage cure schedules at 110°C to 190°C. The majority of the laminates were cured for one hour, but a few were hot pressed for two and four hours. The results, in Fig. 7, indicate a stronger dependence of softening point on the cure temperature than was observed in the PR laminates. The softening temperature does not increase with increasing cure times greater than one hour, so we can assume that the reaction must be complete.

Fig. 7 T.M.A. results from WL series laminates with varying thermal histories.

It is clear from these tests that the curing characteristics of the modified resin (PR series) are substantially different from those of the conventional (WL series) epoxy-resin.

MECHANICAL TESTING

The aim of this part of the work was to select mechanical tests which might be sensitive to variations in the properties of the resin. Clearly conventional tensile tests would be unsuitable since they reflect fibre dominated properties. Accordingly we selected the interlaminar shear test (ILSS) and a fracture toughness test in which the fracture was caused to propagate parallel to the fibre direction. The double torsion test (DTT) configuration was selected because test piece preparation was simple and also, since the stress intensity factor remains constant as the crack propagates a constant force should be recorded throughout the test [3, 4].

The DTT test configuration is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Schematic diagram of a double torsion test performed on a unidirectional composite specimen.

Fig. 9 Load/displacement trace from a double torsion test with the crack length, a , superimposed by means of an event marker.

The extension was increased monotonically (crosshead speed 0.5 mm/min) and indicator marks were made on the load-extension trace at each 5mm increment in crack length as shown in Fig. 9. The strain energy release rate, G , was given by

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2t} \times \frac{dC}{da}$$

The DTT results for the same series of laminates are shown in Fig. 11. Again there is little difference in G for the different cure temperatures. However when the DTT test was carried out at elevated temperature (Fig. 12) on two of the laminates a distinct difference in the G values was observed. A test temperature of 100°C shows a very clear indication of the difference in resin state.

Fig.12 Variation of G with the temperature at which the double torsion test was performed for two WL series laminates cured at 120°C and 180°C.

DISCUSSION

The DSC technique appears to be inadequate for completely characterising the state of cure in the resin systems studied. The most useful thermal analysis technique was the three-point bending softening temperature determination which appears to be sensitive to variations in the cure schedule over a range of temperatures and times relevant to industrial processing conditions.

It has proved to be difficult to correlate the thermal analysis data with mechanical properties. The ILSS technique and the DTT conducted at room temperature both appear to be insensitive to variations in cure schedule which show significant differences in softening temperature. However when the DTT test was carried out at temperatures of 80-110°C it appeared that it was sensitive to the cure applied to the laminates in question.

Both the softening point test and the DTT as applied in this work might be expected to reflect differences in either resin or interface properties, or both. In addition in specimens with imperfect fibre alignment there is the possibility that G might be affected by fibres which bridge the crack. We did observe that P tended to rise slightly as the crack propagated (Fig.9) and it was conjectured that this might be due to fibre bridging. Accordingly a laminate with fibres deliberately misaligned ($\pm 3^\circ$) was fabricated and tested. The results were in fact indistinguishable from those from the well-aligned laminates (open square symbol on Fig. 11). We therefore conclude that fibre bridging does not significantly affect the value of G determined by the DTT test.

CONCLUSIONS

The DSC and modified softening temperature techniques of thermal analysis may be used to characterise the "state of cure" in epoxy resin laminates. However, different resin systems behave in quite different ways so that no single criterion can be applied to all systems.

Mechanical testing techniques appeared to be generally insensitive to the state of resin cure. The ILSS and DTT, both conducted at room temperature, were not useful for characterising the laminates studied. The only technique to show promise was the DTT conducted at an elevated temperature.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Most of the work described was carried out with support from the Procurement Executive Ministry of Defence. We would particularly like to acknowledge the valuable discussions we have had with Dr. G. Dorey of the Royal Aircraft Establishment and with Mr. C. Evans of Westland Helicopters Ltd. who also supplied some of the laminates and other materials.

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